

Genotypic variation in rice susceptibility to boron deficiency

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Rice, despite being relatively insensitive to boron (B) deficiency (Rerkasem et al 1988, Rerkasem and Jamod 1997), suffers from this disorder in Pakistan (Chaudhary et al 1977) and elsewhere (Shorrocks 1997). For example, about 0.6 million ha of rice in Pakistan suffer from B deficiency (NFDC 1998). Although B fertilization is the simplest and most cost-effective solution to the problem, various practical constraints prohibit its adoption by farmers cultivating low-B soils. Genetic variation in B acquisition and efficiency in biomass production is manipulated in many crop species for managing B deficiency (Rerkasem and Jamod 1997). Therefore, we studied some major rice cultivars in Pakistan for their comparative B efficiency.

A greenhouse study was conducted using a B-deficient (hot water extractable B 0.08 mg kg⁻¹) silty clay loam surface soil (0–20 cm) of the Rajar series (Typic Ustortents) with pH (1:1) 8.0, EC 0.27 dS m⁻¹, CaCO₃ equivalent to 3.2%, organic matter 0.38%, and AB-DTPA extractable nutrient contents (mg kg⁻¹): NO₃-N, 1.2;

phosphorus (P), 0.07; potassium (K), 68; zinc (Zn), 0.56; and copper (Cu), 2.3. Four cultivars each of basmati types (fine aromatic—e.g., Super Basmati, Basmati 6129, Basmati 385, and Basmati 370) and IRRI types (medium-long grain/coarse grain, e.g., DR83, KS282, Pakhal, and IR6) were used. Four rice seedlings transplanted in 5-kg soil portions, placed in polyethylene-lined plastic pots, were supplied with two rates of B, 0 (control) or 1.5 mg B kg⁻¹ soil as H₃BO₃. Basal fertilization included 800 mg N kg⁻¹, 100 mg P kg⁻¹, 600 mg K kg⁻¹, 10 mg Zn kg⁻¹, and 5 mg Cu kg⁻¹ soil. One-fourth of the dose of N and K and the full dose of the other nutrients were applied before transplanting. The other three-fourths of N and K were applied in three equal splits—30, 45, and 60 d after transplanting, respectively. Soil in all pots was kept continuously flooded by irrigating with deionized water. Pots were arranged in a split-plot design, assigning cultivars to main plots and B to subplots, with three replications. Young whole shoots (< 30 cm tall) of two plants in each pot were sampled

for B analysis. Grain and straw yield of the remaining two plants were recorded at maturity. Plant tissues were dry-ashed and B concentration in the digests was determined colorimetrically using azomethine-H.

Boron deficiency delayed inflorescence by 4 d in all cultivars. Rice cultivars grown without B exhibited differential sensitivity to B deficiency, with susceptibility of Super Basmati > Basmati 6129 > DR83 > KS282 > Basmati 385 > Pakhal > Basmati 370 > IR6 ($P < 0.05$; see table). With B application, a maximum yield increase of 46% over the control was observed in Super Basmati and a minimum of 10% was seen in IR6. Straw yield increase with B fertilization was maximum in Super Basmati (77%) and minimum in Basmati 370 (2%). There was hardly any relationship between magnitude of reduction in grain and straw yields of various cultivars and B deficiency (see table). Half of the basmati (fine aromatic) and IRRI varieties (coarse grain) yielded >20% more with B application. The cultivars' sensitivity to B

Mean grain and straw yield, B concentration in young whole shoots, and B uptake by rice cultivars as affected by B application to a B-deficient soil.

Cultivar	Grain yield ^a (g plant ⁻¹)		Straw yield ^a (g plant ⁻¹)		B concentration in whole shoots ^a (mg kg ⁻¹)		B uptake ^a (mg plant ⁻¹)		Fertilizer B recovery (% of applied B)	Agronomic efficiency (g grain g ⁻¹ applied B)
	Control	+B	Control	+B	Control	+B	Control	+B		
	Super Basmati	22	31	95 fg	168 d	4.50 fg	7.00 de	549 g		
Basmati 6129	17	23	239 b	268 a	4.60 fg	5.60 ef	1339 de	2338 b	0.13	746
DR83	38	46	74 gh	107 f	5.50 efg	10.00 ab	591 g	1182 a	0.08	1120
KS282	39	47	78 gh	86 fg	5.30 fg	10.70 a	553 g	960 f	0.05	886
Basmati 385	35	41	202 c	277 a	4.26 fg	7.71 cd	1256 de	2698 a	0.19	1054
Pakhal	36	42	59 h	79 gh	4.30 fg	8.00 cd	517 g	954 f	0.06	894
Basmati 370	30	34	167 d	171 d	3.94 g	8.60 bc	894 f	1635 c	0.10	614
IR6	40	44	135 e	156 de	5.50 efg	8.91 bc	696 g	1330 de	0.08	534
LSD (0.05)	3.6	3.6	21	21	1.47	1.47	177	177		

^aValues within a parameter followed by different letters are significantly different at $P < 0.05$.

deficiency was not related to grain length/fineness or biomass produced per plant (see table). Contrary to the belief that B deficiency hampers grain setting more than vegetative growth (Rerkasem and Jamod 1997), the magnitude of straw biomass reduction was greater than grain yield reduction in Super Basmati, DR83, Basmati 385, and Pakhal.

Rice cultivars differed significantly in B uptake when grown under identical environmental conditions. For example, Basmati 6129 was 2.6 times more efficient in using B from B-deficient soil than Pakhal ($P < 0.05$; see table). Despite its higher B use efficiency, however, Basmati 6129 was more susceptible to B deficiency than Pakhal (see table). Fertilizer B recovery is the fraction of applied B taken up in aboveground plant parts, while agronomic efficiency refers to extra grain yield over

the control yield per unit of applied B. Boron-efficient and -inefficient rice genotypes were distinguishable by B concentration in their B-deficient plant tissues, B uptake, fertilizer B recovery, and agronomic efficiency (see table).

Basmati is famous for its aroma and long, fine grains. As Super Basmati, a premier basmati cultivar in Pakistan, was more sensitive to B deficiency than other basmati varieties, the situation is rather alarming because of widespread low soil B in Pakistan (NFDC 1998) and elsewhere (Shorrocks 1997). Boron efficiency is believed to be a single gene-controlled trait. Therefore, tailoring or selecting plant genotypes for B-deficient soils might be more practical than changing the soil to fit the plant. Genetic manipulation, through an efficient molecular approach, could help transfer the B-efficient trait of

Basmati 370 or IR6 into currently popular fine aromatic varieties such as Super Basmati.

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Effect of mixing black clay soil and organic amendment on properties of coarse-textured soil and rice yield

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In Tamil Nadu, rice is grown on coarse-textured soils across a significant area with marginal yields. To improve soil, water, and nutrient retention and to enhance rice yields, a field experiment was conducted during the wet seasons of 1996-97 and 1997-98 (October-January), with each season trial done in one of two adjacent fields. Treatments used were different incorporation levels of black clay soil (0, 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 t ha⁻¹), with or without 25 t raw coir pith ha⁻¹, replicated thrice in a randomized block design. The black clay soil and coir pith were mixed with the puddled soil up to 20 cm depth by trampling and leveling before transplanting. At the beginning of the experiment, soil in control plots had comparable properties such as contents of clay, silt, organic carbon, total N, P, K, Ca, and Mg, available N, P, K, and exchangeable Ca and Mg, electrical conductivity (EC), pH, and cation ex-

change capacity (CEC) as the soil in the rest of the field. Rice varieties IR60 and ADT36 (parentage: local variety, Triveni/IR20) were grown in the first and second croppings, respectively. Grain and straw yield were recorded. Neither field supported any crop other than the wet-season rice crop under study. The soil was coarse-textured throughout the solum of 2 m and was classified as a coarse loamy, kaolinitic, nonacid, isomegathemic Typic Ustipsamment.

Postharvest soil samples (0–20 cm) were analyzed for particle size (International Pipette), organic carbon (chromic acid), EC and pH (saturation paste extract), NH₄OAc-CEC, Kjeldahl-total N, Pemberton-total P, total K (Stanford and English), total Ca and Mg (Versonate), available N (KMnO₄), Olsen P, and NH₄OAc-extractable K, Ca, and Mg.

All soil properties were influenced

by treatments (see table). For incremental amendments of 20 t black clay soil ha⁻¹, there was progressive improvement in most of the parameters, which might have enhanced crop yield. Addition of coir pith alone or in combination with black clay soil helped boost levels of available N, K, and organic carbon. Reduction in total soil K, Ca, and Mg due to coir pith addition suggested soil dissolution by organic acids produced during decomposition of coir pith, which might have promoted increased nutrient availability to the crop. The significant increase in CEC of sandy soil due to the addition of black clay soil may have enhanced nutrient retention and minimized leaching of nutrients, as low CEC can constrain crop performance in coarse-textured soils.

Addition of coir pith alone to sandy soil markedly decreased soil pH, indicating the acidifying effect of organic acid pro-